

India's Urban Agglomeration Growth: A Focus

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Abstract:- In the current context, India's urbanisation is progressing at a quicker rate, although just one-third of the population lives in cities. Only over 30% of the world's population lived in cities in 1950, but by 2012, that number had risen to more than 50%. According to estimates, India's urban population accounted for around 10% of the world's urban population and about 21% of Asia's. According to a UN estimate, by 2030, more than 70% of the world's population would be living in cities. Furthermore, it is estimated that urban regions will house 40.76 percent of India's population. India is in the midst of a tremendous urban shift, and its urban population is the world's second largest behind China's. Natural growth and rural-to-urban migration have both contributed to India's urbanisation. In India, urban poverty has arisen as a result of a lack of employment possibilities and inadequate income among a significant portion of the urban population. Therefore, this paper focuses on India's urban agglomeration growth.

Keyword:- urbanisation, urban growth agglomeration, towns and cities, population growth.

I. INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is a contentious topic since it is influenced by a variety of elements in different social contexts. These variables are subject to alter over time. While population density is a crucial component in urbanisation in some definitions, patterns of behaviour and relationships are important in the process of urbanisation in others. The emergence of a great tradition characterises primary urbanisation, as evidenced by the ancient civilizations of Mohenjo-Daro, Indus Valley, Egypt, Rome, and Mesopotamia. Primary urbanization's goal is to align political, economic, educational, intellectual, and artistic activities with Great Tradition's norms. Secondary urbanisation occurred during the city's industrial phase, resulting in migration, increased trade and commerce activities, and the establishment of production units in cities, as well as the influence of formal regulatory and administrative bodies and institutions, resulting in a new type of society that is easily characterised by heterogeneity and the replacement of traditional values and norms. Secondary urbanisation, which resulted in the breakdown of great tradition, is defined as this cultural shift. Both of these processes result in cultural shifts in cities. Secondary urbanisation is regarded as parasitic in character, as it results in colonialism, capitalism, depletion of key resources, and deterioration of social bonds, relationships, and shared standards. The movement of people into towns and cities and away from rural areas occurs as cities grow in population, partly due to natural growth but primarily due to

individuals migrating from rural areas in quest of the economic opportunities associated with urban life.

II. INDIA'S URBANIZATION

India's urbanisation is largely due to the country's economic liberalisation in the 1990s, which resulted in the rise and development of the private sector. At the moment, urbanisation is moving at a faster pace. In India, around a third of the population lives in cities. According to the 2011 census, India has 53 cities with a population of one million or more; this figure is expected to climb to 87 by 2031. Some of these metropolitan areas will grow into huge economic powerhouses, with GDPs exceeding those of countries like Israel, Portugal, and the United Arab Emirates. Given the high number of people in a compact region and the significant economies of scale that provide jobs, housing, and services, cities are meant to be the key centre for sustainable development. It is critical to properly comprehend Indian cities' ecological, economic, and social sustainability potential. In the current urbanisation context, this can only be accomplished through good inclusive urban design. The Indian government is obliged to allocate funding to various programmes and initiatives in order to renew and rebuild urban spaces. Relationships between the private and public sectors can also be a helpful strategy to dealing with urbanization-related concerns, particularly in terms of providing transportation, reliable water supply, contemporary sewage treatment, and an effective solid waste management system.

III. URBAN AREA CRITERIA

Different criteria are used to define an urban or urban place or area: a) Population size; b) Population density; c) Prominent economic activity; and d) Administrative Structure. According to the United Nations. There are three sorts of urban areas: a) Administrative, based on the form of government; b) Economic, based on the working population's economic activity, with no more than a certain percentage of their economically active population involved in agriculture. c) Ecological states are agglomerations that cover the globally approved criteria of locality as population clusters within dense settlement outlines, regardless of administrative delimitations, size, or economic kind. In India's 1961 Census, a well-defined definition of urban was adopted, according to which an urban region includes: [1] a population density of not less than one thousand people per square mile; [2] a population size of 5000 or more people. [3] Non-agricultural occupations should account for three-quarters of the population. The following are the definitions of urban area from the 2001 and 2011 censuses:

- Any location with a municipality, municipal corporation, cantonment board, or notified town area committee, for example. Statutory towns are a type of urban entity that is notified by law by the relevant state/UT government.
- Other locations with – 1) A population of at least 5000 people is required. 2) At least 75% of the working male

population is employed in non-agricultural jobs. 3) A population density of at least 400 people per square kilometre. Census towns are a type of town that falls into this category. The towns were divided into six groups based on their population in the 2001 Census, as follows:

Classification of Towns	Size of Population
Class I Towns	Less than 1,00,000 population
Class II Towns	50,000 to 99,999 population
Class III Towns	20,000 to 49,999 population
Class IV Towns	10,000 to 19,999 population
Class V Towns	5000 to 9,999 population
Class VI Towns	Less than 5000 population

Table 1

IV. OUTGROWTHS AND URBAN AGGLOMERATIONS

Table 1.1 shows the increase in the number of municipalities, UAs, and OGs during the last ten years. The rapid expansion of urbanisation has resulted in a jump in the number of statutory towns from 3799 in 2001 to 4041 now (2011). From 2001 to 2011, census towns ranged from 1362 to 3894, UAs from 384 to 475, and OGs from 962 to 981. According to the 2011 Census, the country has 7935 towns. In the last ten years, the number of towns has increased by

2774. The population of these 7935 towns accounted for 31.16 percent of the total urban population. Many of these communities are governed by UAs, while others are self-governing. There are five megacities in the country, each with a population of more than 10 million people. Greater Mumbai has a population of 18.4 million, Delhi has a population of 16.3 million, Kolkata has a population of 14.1 million, Chennai has a population of 8.7 million, and Bangalore has a population of 8.7 million (8.5 million).

Type of Towns/UAs/OGs	Number of Towns		Increase in 2001 - 2011
	2001	2011	
Towns:	7935	5161	2774
a) Statutory Town	3799	4041	242
b) Census Towns	1362	3894	2532
Urban Agglomerations	384	475	91
Out Growths	962	981	19

Table 2: Outgrowths and the Number of Towns/Urban Agglomerations (2001 & 2011)

Source: Census of India, 2001 & 2011

Statutory Town indicates places with a municipality, corporation, cantonment board or notified town area committee, etc.

Census Towns comprises of a minimum population of 5,000; at least 75 per cent of the male main working population engaged in non-agricultural pursuits; and a density of population of at least 400 persons per sq. km.

Urban Agglomerations (UAs) must consist of at least a statutory town and its total population (i.e., all the constituents put together) should not be less than 20,000 as per the 2001 Census.

Outgrowths OGs are viable units such as a village or a hamlet or an enumeration block made up of such village or hamlet and clearly identifiable in terms of its boundaries and location.

V. GROWTH OF INDIA'S URBAN AGGLOMERATIONS AND TOWNS

Table 1.2 shows the expansion of Urban Agglomerations (UAs) and towns in India by size/class from 1901 to 2011, indicating the rise of million-plus cities and their populations as a result of the recent rapid urbanisation phenomenon. Overurbanization or pseudo-urbanization is a term used to describe India's urbanisation, in which people move to cities due to rural push rather than urban pull. Only approximately a fifth of the increase in urban population between 2001 and 2011 can be attributed to migration, while more than a third can be attributed to changes in classification, as the economic character of settlements shifts away from agricultural to non-farm activity. The remainder is attributed to urban population increase. In the first wave of globalisation, new cities sprang up as transit hubs thanks to railways, hill stations and cantonments for the governing elite, and market towns for exporting agricultural products. Megacities are very big urban agglomerations having populations of more than 10 million people. The three cities classified as very large UAs in this category are Greater Mumbai UA (18.4 million), Delhi UA (16.3 million), and

Kolkata UA (14.1 million). These cities are home to almost 43% of India's urban population. The number of million-plus cities has steadily increased from 5 in 1951 to 35 in 2001 to 53 in 2011. In 2011, India has 53 urban agglomerations with a population of one million or more, compared to 35 in 2001.

In 2011, 31.2 percent of India's urban population lived in 6171 towns and 495 UAs, compared to 27.8% in over 4368 towns and over 380 UAs in 2001. According to the 2011 Census, Class I UAs/Towns are home to 264.9 million people, or 70% of the total urban population. Out of the 468 UAs/Towns in the Class I category, 53 UAs/Towns with populations of one million or more are known as Million Plus UAs/Cities and are the country's major metropolitan centres. These Million Plus UAs/Cities are home to 160.7 million people (or 42.6 percent of the urban population). Since the previous Census in the country, 18 new UAs/Towns have been added to the list. As seen in the graph, the urban population of class I towns increased from 1981 to 2011 when compared to class II, III, IV, V, and VI towns. In all of India's main urbanised states, however, the share of urban population of class III, IV, V, and VI has decreased. This demonstrates that, in comparison to class II, III, IV, V, and VI cities, the predominant population trend is

towards class I cities. The population of class I towns has been steadily increasing throughout the years.

Because of the rapidly growing number of municipalities, the current phase of urbanisation is likely to intensify. The collapse of urban basic services such as housing, water supply, drainage, sanitation, and other infrastructure, particularly in slum areas, occurred as a result of the huge population size of the main cities. The population of large cities has exploded, resulting in a near collapse of urban services and quality of life. The demographic explosion and poverty-induced rural-urban migration have accounted for urbanisation. Both large and small cities are experiencing an increase in urban agglomeration. During the post-reform period, 16 cities were added to the list of cities with populations of one million or more. In 1991, there were more than 22 million cities, which climbed to 32 in 2001 and 38 in 2011. In India, the pattern of urbanisation is defined by a constant concentration of people and activities in large cities. People migrate from rural areas to urban areas in pursuit of work and a better standard of living. Due to the uneven regional distribution of urban population, this has resulted in imbalanced urban expansion.

Census Years	All Classes	No. of Towns by Size/Class						Percentage of Urban Population by Size/Class					
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
1901	1811	24	43	130	391	744	479	26.0	11.2	15.6	20.8	20.1	6.1
1911	1754	23	40	135	364	707	485	27.4	10.5	16.4	19.7	19.3	6.5
1921	1894	29	45	145	370	734	571	29.7	10.3	15.9	18.2	18.6	7
1931	2017	35	56	183	434	800	509	31.2	11.6	16.8	18	17.1	5.2
1941	2190	49	74	242	498	920	407	38.2	11.4	16.3	15.7	15	3.1
1951	2795	76	91	327	608	1124	569	44.6	9.9	15.7	13.6	12.9	3.1
1961	2270	102	129	437	719	711	172	51.4	11.2	16.9	12.7	6.8	0.7
1971	2476	148	173	558	827	623	147	57.2	10.9	16	10.9	4.4	0.4
1981	3301	218	270	743	1059	758	253	60.3	11.6	14.3	9.5	3.5	0.5
1991	3696	300	345	947	1167	740	197	65.2	10.9	13.1	7.7	2.6	0.3
2001	4368	393	401	1151	1344	888	191	68.6	9.67	12.2	6.8	2.3	0.2
2011	6171	468	474	1373	1683	1749	424	70.2	8.5	11.1	6.4	3.4	0.4

Table 3: Growth of India's Urban Agglomerations and Towns by Size, Class, and Category (1901–2011)

Source: Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, 2001, Census of 2011

Class I: Greater than 100,000 population Class II: 50,000-100,000 population

Class III: 20,000-50,000 population Class IV: 10,000-20,000 population

Class V: 5000-10,000 population Class VI: Less than 5000 population

VI. URBAN GROWTH'S CONTRIBUTION

Table 1.3 shows the split of urban growth into three primary components: natural rise, net rural-urban classification, and net rural-urban migration. Natural population growth contributed 43.8 percent to urban population growth from 2001 to 2011, compared to 58 percent from 1991 to 2001. Despite the natural rise in population, it is commonly assumed that urbanisation is

exclusively due to rural-urban migration. The data in the preceding table plainly shows that net rural-urban migration is quite low. Furthermore, from roughly 21.5 percent in 1991-2001 to 35.6 percent in 2001-2011, the contribution of net reclassification of rural to urban areas, changes in municipal boundaries, and out growths has increased dramatically. In comparison to net rural to urban migration, this has been the most important factor determining the speed of urbanisation during the 2000s. According to the

2011 Census, there has been a massive growth in the number of towns in India, indicating that there has been restructuring of rural urban spaces and that many of the new

towns have come up as part of urban agglomeration in cities with populations of one million or more in 2000.

Census Years	Number of Cities	Population (In Million)	Share in Total Urban Population (%)
1901	1	1.51	5.84
1911	2	2.76	10.65
1921	2	3.13	11.14
1931	2	3.41	10.18
1941	2	5.31	12.02
1951	5	11.75	18.81
1961	7	18.1	22.93
1971	9	27.83	25.51
1981	12	42.12	26.41
1991	23	70.66	32.54
2001	35	108.34	37.87
2011	53	160.71	42.62

Table 4: India's Urban Growth Contribution (1971–2011)

Source: Bhagat R. B. (2018)

Components	Population (In million)				Percentage Distribution			
	1971-1981	1981-1991	1991-2001	2001-2011	1971-1981	1981-1991	1991-2001	2001-2011
Urban increment	49.9	56.8	68.2	91	100	100	100	100
Natural Increase (of initial population plus inter-censal migrants)	24.9	35.4	39.3	39.9	50	62.3	57.6	43.8
Net rural-urban migration	9.3	10.6	14.2	18.7	18.6	18.7	20.8	20.6
Net classification from rural to urban including jurisdictional changes and outgrowths	15.7	10.8	14.7	32.3	31.4	19	21.5	35.6

Table 5: Population, Number, and Percentage India's Metropolitan Cities as a Percentage of Total Urban Population (1901–2011)

Source: India Stat – Ministry of Urban Employment and Poverty Alleviation, Government of India

VII. METROPOLITAN CITIES' PROPORTION

The process of urbanisation has resulted in the emergence of metropolitan cities. A large majority of India's urban population lives in cities with populations of one million or more. Table 1.4 displays the number of million-plus cities in the United States over the last century, as well as their growth. According to the data, the country only had one such city around the turn of the century, in 1901. In 1911, the number increased to two and remained consistent until 1941. Apart from the total number of cities, the total population of these cities has increased dramatically over the decades, as has its proportion to the total urban population. By 2001, the country had 35 million or more cities, with these cities accounting for roughly 38 percent of the

country's total urban population. In 2011, this number increased to 53 cities, accounting for almost 43% of the entire urban population.

VIII. CONCLUSION

As a result, urbanisation can be defined as a process that manifests itself in a specific society's demographic, social, economic, technological, and environmental elements of life through temporal, geographical, and sectoral changes. The term "urbanisation" refers to the gradual concentration of people in urban areas. The beginning of the contemporary, worldwide process of urbanisation is a relatively new phenomenon, closely linked to the industrial revolution and economic prosperity. In India, urbanisation is partly owing to economic liberalisation in the 1990s, which

ushered in privatisation and the growth of the private sector. Even though India's urbanisation is progressing at a quicker rate, barely one-third of the population lives in cities. Only over 30% of the world's population lived in cities in 1950, but by 2012, that number had risen to more than 50%. According to estimates, India's urban population accounted for around 10% of the world's urban population and about 21% of Asia's. According to a UN estimate, by 2030, more than 70% of the world's population would be living in cities. Furthermore, it is estimated that urban regions will house 40.76 percent of India's population. According to this analysis, India is in the midst of a tremendous urban shift. After China, India has the world's second-largest urban population. Natural growth and rural-to-urban migration have both contributed to India's urbanisation. In India, urban poverty has arisen as a result of a lack of employment possibilities and inadequate income among a significant portion of the urban population. Components of urban expansion can be divided into three categories: Natural growth, net migration, and area re-classification are the three main contributors, with natural growth accounting for 41.7 percent between 1971 and 1981 and 58.7 percent between 1981 and 1991. During 1971-81, net migration and changes in municipal boundaries accounted for 39.4 percent of the total, but this fell to 22 percent in 1981-91. One aspect of the transformation is the movement of employment from farmland to urban-based industry and services.

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